

ISic3715

I.Sicily inscription 3715

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

limestone

Object

stele

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

found in the 'temple of Demeter' (i.e. S. Biagio)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 44219

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136031

1. [?Δί] φν Ἐχίπ [που - - -]

Edition: PHI336051

1. [(?)Δί] φν Ἐχίπ [που — — —]

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 136031

PHI 336051

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1266.7

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 36 no.7 fig.84

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